

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Sigad****FIRST NAME: Isman Wais****PROGRAM CODE: DEOH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author uses Zotero to insert references

The author uses Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 2%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the Chicago Manual of Style primarily used for?
 - Fiction writing.
 - Formatting academic papers and research.**¹
 - Creative writing.
 - Business reports.
2. How has the Chicago Manual of Style impacted academic writing and citation practices over time?
 - It has standardized citation formats across all academic disciplines.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 13–14.

- It has evolved to include updated guidelines for digital materials and online sources.²**
- It has eliminated the need for footnotes in academic writing.
- It has discouraged the use of bibliographies in research papers.
3. What are the primary differences between the notes-bibliography style and the author-date style of citation, and in which contexts is each style typically used?
- The notes-bibliography style is used primarily in the humanities, while the author-date style is favored in the natural and physical sciences.³**
- The notes-bibliography style requires in-text citations, while the author-date style does not.
- The author-date style is more detailed than the notes-bibliography style.
- Both styles are used interchangeably across all academic disciplines.
4. In what ways has the advent of the digital age altered citation practices in academic writing? Discuss at least two notable changes that have come about due to digital technologies and give examples of new citation formats or tools designed to aid researchers and writers in organizing their citations.
- The digital age has made citation practices more complex, with no new tools or formats emerging to help writers.

² Turabian, 13–14.

³ Turabian, 13.

- Digital technologies have simplified citation practices by allowing for automated citation generation through tools like Zotero and EndNote and have introduced formats like Chicago 17th Edition that accommodate online sources.⁴**
- The digital age has had little impact on citation practices, as traditional methods remain the same.
- Citation practices have become less critical in the digital age, as most information is available online and does not require citation.
5. You are tasked with writing a research paper on the challenges faced by the National Social Security Fund of Djibouti in strengthening worker's health and safety. Your paper includes academic journal articles, government reports, and interviews with local health officials. Which citation style would be most appropriate for your paper, and why?
- The notes-bibliography style allows for detailed footnotes and is suitable for various sources.
- Author-date style because it is commonly used in social sciences and provides precise in-text citations for various types of sources.⁵**
- Any style, as long as you are consistent throughout the paper.
- No citation style is needed since the topic is specific to Djibouti.

⁴ Turabian, 14.

⁵ Turabian, 13.

6. Why is it crucial to use proper citation in academic writing, and how does it contribute to academic integrity and effective scholarly communication? Additionally, what might happen if sources need to be cited correctly?

Proper citation is essential because it gives credit to original authors and allows readers to verify sources. Failing to cite can lead to plagiarism accusations and damage one's academic reputation.⁶

Proper citation is not very important as long as the ideas are original. The only consequence of failing to cite is that the paper may receive a lower grade.

Proper citation is only necessary for published works. Failing to cite sources correctly will not have any significant consequences.

Proper citation is essential for aesthetic reasons. Failing to cite sources correctly may confuse readers but does not have serious consequences.

7. The literature review includes the following poorly formatted reference: "Ali, M. 2020. Health and Safety in Djibouti. *Journal of Public Health*, 15(2): 100-110." What is the correct format for this reference according to WHO style?

Ali, M. 2020. "Health and Safety in Djibouti." *Journal of Public Health* 15 (2): 100-110.⁷

Ali, M. "Health and Safety in Djibouti." *Journal of Public Health* 15, no. 2 (2020): 100-110.

⁶ Turabian, 139.

⁷ World Health Organization (WHO), *WHO Style Guide*, 2nd Ed (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 42.

- Ali, M. 2020. Health and Safety in Djibouti. *Journal of Public Health* 15, no. 2: 100-110.
 - Ali, M. 2020. "Health and Safety in Djibouti." *Journal of Public Health* 15: 100-110.
8. Compare and contrast the notes-bibliography and author-date styles regarding their strengths and weaknesses. In what types of research contexts might one be preferred over the other?
- The notes-bibliography style is preferred in humanities disciplines for its detailed citation format, while the author-date style is favored in social sciences for its brevity and clarity.⁸**
 - The author-date style allows for more comprehensive footnotes, making it ideal for historical research, whereas the notes-bibliography style needs to be more flexible.
 - The notes-bibliography style is less commonly used in academic writing, while the author-date style is universally accepted across all disciplines.
 - The author-date style is more suitable for literary analysis, while the notes-bibliography style is better for empirical research.
9. In the literature review, the author cites a report by the Djibouti Ministry of Health: "The health and safety of workers is paramount for economic development" (Djibouti

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 179–82.

Ministry of Health, 2021). What is the correct way to format this citation in WHO style?

- “The health and safety of workers is paramount for economic development” (Djibouti Ministry of Health 2021).
- “The health and safety of workers is paramount for economic development” (Djibouti Ministry of Health, 2021).⁹**
- “The health and safety of workers is paramount for economic development” (Djibouti Ministry of Health, 2021, p. 10).
- “The health and safety of workers is paramount for economic development” (Djibouti Ministry of Health 2021, 10).

10. What is the primary purpose of the Euclid style in academic writing?

- To enhance creative expression
- To provide a standardized format for citations and references¹⁰**
- To simplify the writing process
- To promote informal writing

⁹ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, 42.

¹⁰ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth (Washington, D.C: Euclid University Press, 2024), 41.

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WHO, World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. 2nd Ed. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.